

COMPRESSION MOLDING 3D-CAE OF DISCONTINUOUS LONG FIBER REINFORCED POLYAMIDE 6: INFLUENCE ON CAVITY FILLING AND DIRECT FIBER SIMULATIONS OF VISCOSITY FITTING METHODS

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ABSTRACT

For the purpose of weight reduction, the use of lightweight materials is progressing in automotive industry. The discontinuous long fiber reinforced thermoplastic sheets called the random mats (the RM) are also a candidate for the lightweight materials. The RM containing randomly distributed flexible long fibers is molded by the compression. During the molding, the RM melts are placed on the lower mold which is controlled to below crystallization temperature of the matrix resin, and are promptly compressed by the upper mold down. At this time, the RM melts flow in the cavity while being cooled by the mold. Prediction technologies for the cavity filling and flexible long fiber behavior are necessary. On the other hand, the compression molding CAE (Computer Aided Engineering) is not established enough.

In the present work, a suitable measuring method for the viscosity change of the RM melts was clarified. And a suitable fitting method by plural viscosity equations was also proposed in order to improve the fitting precision. In addition, the cavity filling simulations in the compression molding were performed using the new fitting method. The effectiveness of the method was shown. Furthermore, the direct fiber simulations in the compression molding were also performed. Local positions that bending of the flexible long fiber occur could be predicted in the cavity.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well known that various improvement technologies for fuel efficiency have been developed from the viewpoint of environmental conservation and oil resource exhaustion. One of the practical ways is to reduce the vehicle weight by replacing parts made of steels with those made of lighter materials [e.g., 1]. As an example, the replacement by discontinuous long fiber reinforced thermoplastic parts that are molded in the compression has been carried out. The reinforced thermoplastic with a sheet shape is called a random mat (hereinafter referred to as RM). The long fibers that are contained in the RM are randomly oriented in the plane. In comparison with the injection molding, there are very few breaks of the long fiber in the compression molding. In other words, the residual long fibers after the molding can almost keep initial length. The RM has potentials of excellent specific strength, specific stiffness, and moldability. On the other hand, whether these potentials can be applied to industrial parts actually, it is dependent on condition of the molding process. Therefore, as the prediction technology, establishment of the compression molding CAE (Computer Aided Engineering) that can be utilized in industry are needed. The compression molding using the RM consists of six processes roughly. Those are the cutting process, the pre-heating process, the transfer process (from an oven to

the mold), the cavity filling process, the pressure holding and cooling process, and the demolding process.

In the previous study, there is a small number of reports [2-6] about the compression molding CAE, in comparison with the injection molding CAE. Most of those reports were analyzed the molding by the thermosetting SMC (Sheet Molding Compound). In the case of the RM that made of thermoplastic, it is also important to analyze temperature decrease by air cooling when the RM heated by the oven is carried to the mold. But there were no reports of the analysis in consideration of this temperature decrease, in the range that we searched. One reason why the compression molding CAE technologies do not readily evolve is that the viscosity measurement method of the RM melts is not established enough. The viscosity is one of the most important material property for the CAE. As will be described later, the capillary rheometer is not usable in the measurement of this plastic melts. But, because the melt viscosity is significantly influenced by both temperature and shear rate, the measurements of these dependencies are necessary. Moreover, viscosity equation fitting method that can faithfully represent actual change of the viscosity is also required. In particular, for the viscosity change of the resin cooled to around the crystallization temperature, the fitting that kept the high consistency was difficult.

In addition, flow-induced behavior analyses of flexible long fibers are also important for the compression molding using the RM. The current injection molding CAE software is applied the conventional methods [e.g., 7] that are improved the original model [8] for anisotropic particle with rigid ellipsoidal shape. The conventional methods had been also examined in the ideal shear and elongation flow field, as academic studies [8-10]. However, those simulations are for short fibers with rigid, and the conventional methods are not suitable for the flexible long fibers because the bending of these fibers cannot be predicted. Recently, trials of several new simulation methods for flexible long fibers are ongoing [11-17]. We have focused on the method called "Direct Fiber Simulation" (DFS). By this DFS, motions of the fibers can be analyzed directly.

Though there are situations as described above, some commercialized CAE software of the compression molding have begun to be sold from a few years ago. But the software has not yet been applied to actual industrial parts at still initial developing stage. Improvement of the CAE technology will be essential for the further development of the RM parts.

In this paper, first, we have proposed both a suitable measuring method of the viscosity change and a suitable viscosity equation fitting method for the RM melts. Second, Cavity filling simulations in the compression molding have been carried out using the suitable viscosity equation fitting method. And the effect of the method has been validated. Third, flexible long fiber behavior analysis has been also performed by the DFS.

2 MATERIAL PROPERTIES

2.1 MATERIAL

In this study, the RM with 2mm thickness made of discontinuous long glass fiber reinforced polyamide6 (L-GFPA6) was used. The concentration of the fibers having a length of from 30 to 50mm is about 45% by volume (in plane random orientation). Before the following measurements, the RM (L-GFPA6) were dried by hot-air more than 12 hours at 80°C every time, in order to remove moisture.

2.2 GENERAL PROPERTY MEASUREMENTS

The Specific heat was measured by a Differential scanning calorimetry (X-DSC7000, Hitachi High-Tech Science Corporation) at cooling mode of -5°C/min. The peak curve was observed at the range from 195°C to 175°C. The peak temperature was about 190°C.

The thermal conductivity was taken by the laser flash method between 30 and 80°C. The average of measurements was 0.48W/m²/°C.

The heat-transfer coefficient is not physical property of the RM (L-GFPA6) exactly, but this is a characteristic value necessary for the CAE. The coefficients between the RM (L-GFPA6) and S50C steel plate(the same material and surface roughness as compression mold) were obtained by the temperature gradient method at several pressures and 190°C. The coefficients were increased with the pressure. The average value from 10 to 60MPa was about 40,000 W/m²/K.

The pressure-volume-temperature behaviors were measured by a PVT measuring apparatus (PVT TEST SYSTEM, Toyo Seiki Seisaku-Sho) of the piston direct pressure method. In cooling and constant pressure mode, measurement conditions were a temperature range from 270 to 50°C and a pressure range from 20 to 120MPa.

2.3 MELT VISCOSITY MEASUREMENTS

2.3.1 SHEAR RATE DEPENDENCY

Firstly, we tried the melt viscosity measurement of the RM (L-GFPA6) by the capillary rheometer, but the long fibers were clogged at the die entrance of the barrel and reproducible data were not obtained.

Secondly, in the static mode, the rotational rheometer (ARES, TA Instruments) with parallel plate fixtures was used. Shear rate dependence of the steady-state viscosity was measured using the plates with a diameter of 25mm. The setting shear rate was changed from 0.01 to 100s⁻¹. The results at 220, 240, and 260°C are shown in Figure 1. At the low shear rate region, data were measured stably. However, when shear rate reached more than 0.25s⁻¹, the RM (L-GFPA6) began to go out of the plates. Because this phenomenon was caused detection values to become unstable, reproducible data were not produced. Only the data at narrow shear rate ranges were provided, but the shear thinning was observed in the RM (L-GFPA6) because the steady-state viscosity decreased with increasing the shear rate.

Thirdly, in the dynamic mode, the rotational rheometer with parallel plate fixtures was also used. Frequency dependence of the complex viscosity was measured using the plates with a diameter of 25mm. The setting frequency was changed from 0.01 to 100rad/s. The maximum strain was varied between 0.001 and 0.1. The results at 240°C are shown in Figure 2. In comparison, the steady-state viscosity was also plotted. The complex viscosity decreased with increasing frequency and was greatly influenced by the maximum strain. And it was observed that the complex viscosity is not equivalent to the steady-state viscosity. But then, at the case of neat resin that is not reinforced by fibers, it is well known that the complex viscosity become almost equivalent to the steady-state viscosity and the Cox-Mertz rule [18] can be basically applied. This rule is described by the following equation:

$$\dot{\eta}(\dot{\gamma}) = \eta^*(\omega) \quad (1)$$

where η is the steady-state viscosity, $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate, η^* is the complex viscosity, and ω is the frequency. By the way, in short fiber reinforced resin with remarkable strain dependence, there are some reports that this rule cannot be applied. As with these reports, in this RM (L-GFPA6), the Cox-Mertz rule could not be also applied. On the other hand, for composite materials with remarkable strain dependence, the extended Cox-Mertz rule [19] has been proposed by Doraiswamy et al., namely

$$\dot{\eta}(\dot{\gamma}) = \eta^*(\gamma_m \omega) \quad (2)$$

where γ_m is the maximum strain. This is the rule for converting the complex viscosity into the steady-state viscosity in consideration of the maximum strains. Figure 3 shows the converted viscosity obtained by shifting the complex viscosity according to the extended Cox-Mertz rule. As a result, the each converted viscosity obtained in different maximum strain was observed good agreement by these shifts. And, the agreement of the converted viscosity and the steady-state viscosity was also good. The

extended Cox-Mertz rule could be applied to this RM (L-GFPA6), since the equivalence between the converted viscosity and the steady-state viscosity was verified. In addition, for the converted viscosity, we tried the viscosity curve fitting by a 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equation [Eq. (3)].

$$\eta_1 = A1 \gamma^{\bullet B1} \exp(C1/T) \quad (3)$$

Here η_1 is the steady-state viscosity, T is temperature, and A1, B1, and C1 are fitting coefficients. The coefficients were decided so that calculated values accorded to measurements as much as possible. Table 1 shows the coefficients used. As the result, except the high shear rate region, this fitting equation was represented the converted shear rate dependence of the converted viscosity. From the results described above, we propose that a suitable method for obtaining the shear rate dependence of the steady-state viscosity for the RM melts (L-GFPA6) is to convert the complex viscosity that was measured in the dynamic mode of the rotational rheometer, by using the extended Cox-Mertz rule. In this indirect way, the steady-state viscosity for the RM melts (L-GFPA6) could be estimated with a wide range of shear rate.

Figure 1: Steady-state viscosity as a function of shear rate at different temperature.

Figure 2: Complex viscosity as a function of frequency at different maximum strain and steady-state viscosity as a function of shear rate.

Figure 3: Converted viscosity as a function of converted shear rate according to the extended Cox-Merz rule given by Eq. (2) and steady-state viscosity as a function of shear rate. Fitting line is the 3-Constant-Arrhenius Eq. (3).

2.3.2 TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCY

We also examined to obtain temperature dependence of the steady-state viscosity. As with the evaluation method of the shear rate dependency, the temperature dependence was estimated by converting complex viscosity according to the extended Cox-Mertz rule, after the dynamic mode measurements by the rotational rheometer. Specific conditions are as follows. The parallel plates of the 8mm diameter were used. While the RM melts (L-GFPA6) were cooled in nitrogen gas from 240 °C to 150 °C at -5 °C/min, complex viscosity data at constant frequency were measured continuously. Because of volume shrinkage of the RM (L-GFPA6) by the temperature drop, the RM melts (L-GFPA6) were applied a low load of about 50g normal force during the measurement. These measurements were carried out at various frequencies. Figure 4 shows temperature dependence of the converted viscosity in each converted shear rate using the extended Cox-Mertz rule. As a characteristic behavior, the temperature dependence was observed to be roughly classified into the following three regions in all converted shear rates. At high temperature (more than 205 °C), the viscosity increases gradually with temperature decrease. At medium temperature (between 192 and 205 °C), the viscosity increases rapidly with temperature decrease. At low temperature (less than 192 °C), the viscosity increases gradually with temperature decrease. In this paper, each region is expressed as “high temperature region”, “transition region”, and “low temperature region” sequentially. With regard to influence of the converted shear rate, as the rate became higher, the converted viscosity became lower at all regions. The start and the end temperature of the transition region became slightly higher with decreasing the converting shear rate, exactly. Here, the DSC under the same cooling rate condition was also measured. From the DSC curve, crystallization exotherm of the polyamide6 was observed in the transition region. The temperature at which the viscosity begins to increase rapidly is slightly higher than that at which the crystallization exotherm begins. But, this crystallization should be a main cause of the rapid viscosity increase in the transition region. In the low temperature region, the converted viscosity remains high, the detected torque had no significant change during cooling.

Additionally, for the temperature dependence, we tried the curve fitting by the WLF fitting equation. Though coefficients were decided so that calculation curves are fitted it to the measurements of the high temperature region as much as possible, the curves increased more gently than the measured values in the Transition region. And the deviation was very large in both the transition region and the low temperature region. In other words, it was not possible to fit by the WLF fitting equation at a

wide temperature range. In order to solve this problem, we make a proposal to use each different fitting equations in the high temperature region, the transition region, and the low temperature region. This time, plural 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations [Eq. (3), (4), and (5)] having different coefficients were used in each region.

$$\eta_2 = A2 \gamma^{\bullet B2} \exp(C2T) \tag{4}$$

$$\eta_3 = A3 \gamma^{\bullet B3} \exp(C3T) \tag{5}$$

Here η_2 and η_3 are the steady-state viscosity, and A2, B2, C2, A3, B3, and C3 are fitting coefficients. The coefficients of the Eq. (3) have been already determined by the shear rate dependence (Figure 1). As can be seen Figure 4, in the high temperature region only, the Eq. (3) was confirmed to be able to fit the converted viscosity. The coefficients of the Eq. (4) and (5) were determined to coincide with the respective temperature dependence of the transition region and the low temperature region. Table 1 shows the coefficients of three equations. It is possible to excellently represent all temperature dependence estimated at different converted shear rates using three 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations.

Figure 4: Converted viscosity as a function of temperature according to the extended Cox-Merz rule given by Eq. (2) at different maximum strain rate. Fitting lines are three 3-Constant-Arrhenius Eq. (3), (4), and (5) for each temperature region.

Eq.(3)			Eq.(4)			Eq.(5)		
A1	B1	C1	A2	B2	C2	A3	B3	C3
1.8E5	-0.8	-0.02	4.0E55	-0.97	-0.59	7.2E6	-1.0	-0.01

Table 1: Values of the coefficients in the three 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations.

3 CAE ANALYSES

3.1 CAVITY FILLING SIMULATION

In order to simulate cavity filling with cooling from the mold in the compression molding process, the CAE software (3D TIMON-CompositePRESS, Toray Engineering Co., Ltd.) was used. This software can analyze in the 3-dimensions by the finite volume method and the Eulerian mesh. After the RM is heated to above the melting point by the oven and is moved on the lower mold, flow of the molten RM proceeds in the cavity while its heat transfers to the mold which is controlled to less than the crystallization temperature. Therefore, fitting equation which can represent accurately the viscosity change during mold process is necessary to the filling analyses. In fact, it should be used the fitting equations that be able to indicate the rapid viscosity increase by temperature decrease.

A subroutine program that we developed originally was added to the CAE software so that the three 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations are usable in the filling simulation. By the subroutine program, calculations proceed as follows. First, average resin temperature at each element was estimated from surrounding node before flow calculation. Second, judging from the temperature region corresponding to this average temperature, one of the three 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations was chosen at each element. Third, by using the appropriate fitting equation for each element, the flow in the cavity was analyzed between initial time steps. By repeating these choices and calculations at each time step, even when the resin temperature decreases remarkably, analyses using suitable viscosity distribution are continued until the end of the filling.

Figure 5 shows dimension of mold cavity (300 x 300 x 20mm) and initial RM (173 x 280 x t6.0mm) for the analyses. The RM thickness that we had measured the properties described above was 2mm. The RMs with 6.0mm thickness are assumed the case which laminated three pieces using those with 2mm thickness. Table 2 shows simulation condition of compression molding. These simulations were started analyses from the time when the RMs heated to 240°C uniformly were taken out of the heating oven. Just before the filling analyses, the cooling temperature analyses of the heated RMs at two steps were carried out. Those were the steps that the RMs are moved from the oven to the lower mold and that the RMs are held on the lower mold until the compression by the upper mold down. In the former, heat transfer with air was analyzed on the entire surface. In the latter, only analysis of the under surface was changed to heat transfer with the lower mold. Continuously, the filling processes were begun to simulate using the RMs with temperature distribution after those analyses.

Figure 5: Analyses dimensions of mold cavity (300 x 300 x H20mm) and initial RM (173 x 280 x t6.0mm) .

Parameters	
Air Temperature	23°C
Initial RM Temperature	240°C
Mold Temperature	140°C
Heat-transfer coefficient between Air and RM	50W/m ² /K
Max. Press Load	1000kN
Increase Rate of Press Load	200kN/sec
Move time from oven to mold	14.5sec
Hold time on the lower mold until compression	13.5sec

Table 2: Simulation condition of the compression molding

Figure 6: Final filling patterns by two kind of viscosity fitting equations. (a) Analysis result using three 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations (Eq. (3), (4) and (5)). (b) Analysis result using one 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equation (Eq. (3)). The color contour is arrival time.

Two kind of viscosity fitting equations were used for the comparison between new and the conventional methods. As the new method, the three 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations [Eq. (3), (4), and (5)] which can accurately represent the viscosity change in a wide temperature range were used. As the conventional method, the one 3- Constant-Arrhenius fitting equation [Eq. (3)] which can accurately represent only the viscosity change in the high temperature region was used. This represent lower viscosity than actual value in the transition region and the low temperature region, as shown in Figure 4. Figure 6 shows simulated results of final filling patterns which were displayed arrival time by the color contour. In the result of the new method (the three 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations), the resin flow stopped on the way without reaching the cavity end and it was unfilled. In that of the conventional method (one 3- Constant-Arrhenius fitting equation), the resin flow completed with reaching at the cavity end and it was filled fully. It seems that the flow by the conventional method is greater than that by actual molding. On the other hand, the flow by the new method must be appropriate, because the equations which can exactly represent the rapid viscosity increase in the transition region were used.

3.2 DIRECT FIBER SIMULATION (DFS)

With regard to simulations of flow-induced fiber behavior, the conventional methods [e.g., 7] are not suitable for flexible long fibers. The bending of these fibers cannot be predicted because the strain rate distribution along the fiber axis is neglected. As an alternative, several direct fiber simulations (DFS) by connecting a number of particles and by connecting a number of rigid rods were examined [11-17]. These DFSs are suitable for flexible long fibers because the strain rate distribution along the fiber axis can be considered. In the model by a number of particles, it is difficult to analyze practical products, because computation time is too long. In the model by a number of rigid rods, it is possible to analyze practical products, because computation time can be shortened.

After the cavity filling analyses, motions of flexible long fibers were simulated by the DFS modeled a number of rigid rods and hinge nodes. The fiber-fiber interactions were neglected. As shown in Figure 6, the flexible long fibers with 24mm length were modeled by 12 rigid rods and 13 hinge nodes.

Figure 6: Schematic model of a flexible long fiber modeled by 12 rods with 13 hinge node.

Figure 7: Analysis of flow-induced flexible long fiber behavior by direct fiber simulation (DFS) in the compression molding. (a) Initial state of the fibers before compression. (b) Final state of the fibers after compression. The color display indicates the degree of the fiber bend. The red fibers have large bend. The blue fibers have slight bend or no bend.

About 34,500 flexible long fibers without bending were located within initial RM (173 x 280 x t6.0mm), in the in-plane random orientation state. Figure 7 shows the DFS result using flow velocity distribution that was analyzed the cavity filling by the three 3-Constant-Arrhenius fitting equations. By the degree of fiber bending, each fiber was distinguished in different color display. In order of degree of large bending, fibers were displayed with red, orange, yellow, green, and blue, respectively. The following results were obtained. Before flow, all flexible long fibers without the bending existed randomly within the RM sheet which was placed in the cavity. During flow, each fiber's position and shape was changed by the strain rate distribution along the fiber length. After the flow stop, it was suggested that many of the bent fibers occurs at the flow front and the cavity edge, because most of the red fibers were recognized at those positions. In this way, we were able to predict the flow-induced behaviors of the flexible long fibers during the cavity filling.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have concluded as follows. First, about a suitable measuring method for the viscosity change of the RM melts, the complex viscosity obtained in the dynamic mode of the rotational rheometer should be converted, according to the extended Cox-Mertz rule. And about a suitable viscosity equation fitting method of the RM melts, the plural equations should be properly used in each temperature region, in order to improve remarkably the fitting precision.

Second, about the cavity filling simulation in the compression molding, by choosing from the plural viscosity fitting equations at each time steps and each element during flow, appropriate calculation could be continued until the flow stop.

Third, about flow-induced behavior simulation of the flexible long fibers in the compression molding, by the direct fiber simulation (DFS) which is connected a number of rigid rods, motions of the fibers could be estimated. And local positions that the bent fibers occur could be predicted.

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